

STRUCTURE-ACTIVITY RELATIONSHIP OF NATURAL 10-MEMBERED LACTONES AND THEIR SEMISYNTHETIC DERIVATIVES

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Abstract

Ten-membered lactones (TMLs) also known as nonenolides are natural products that exhibit diverse biological activities, including phytotoxic, cytotoxic, and antimicrobial effects. Despite their potential, they remain underexplored in terms of structure-activity relationship (SAR) studies. This article reviews preliminary SAR trends among natural and semisynthetic TMLs, identifying key structural motifs – such as α,β -unsaturated ketones, epoxides, allyl alcohol motifs and stereochemical variations – that influence selective toxicity, while also outlining limitations of current SAR methods and prospects for cheminformatics-based analysis.

Introduction

Secondary metabolites serve as an exceptional source of bioactive compounds, providing the basis for many approved drugs and crop protection agents^{1,2}. Among these, ten-membered lactones (TMLs) are a structurally diverse group of molecules featuring a strained medium-sized cyclic core with variable patterns of oxidation, alkylation, and substitution (figure 1). These natural compounds have been isolated from a broad range of organisms – including fungi, bacteria, and occasionally plants and some animals – and exhibit diverse biological activities such as phytotoxicity, cytotoxicity, antimicrobial and insecticidal effects³. Some strains of micromycetes possess biotechnological relevance facilitating biosynthetic production of TMLs⁴. Apart from that, a variety of total synthesis methods have been developed to access their unique structures⁵, including chemical diversification approaches⁶.

Figure 1. Structural diversity of TMLs

Despite the discovery of over a few hundred of natural TMLs, comprehensive structure-activity relationship (SAR) data remain limited. While SAR studies play a crucial role in refining natural products by identifying structural features that drive biological activity, optimize their physicochemical properties, and support target prediction⁷, this approach has not been widely applied for TMLs. Existing bioactivity data are fragmentary: some compounds have been screened across multiple biological models, but most have been tested against only one or two targets, or not tested at all³. To date, only a few SAR models have been proposed – mainly for phytotoxic TMLs with methyl or propyl substituents at C-9⁸⁻¹⁰, and for a small subset of cytotoxic C-2-methylated analogs¹¹⁻¹². Nevertheless, identifying consistent taxophoric motifs remains essential for understanding the bioactivity of this underexplored class of secondary metabolites.

This article summarises the current SAR data derived from natural TMLs and their semisynthetic derivatives with particular attention to chemical features that influence selective toxicity. Due to this inconsistency in toxicity profiling, the relationships described below should be regarded as preliminary trends rather than definitive rules.

Proposed taxophores of TMLs

α,β -Unsaturated keto group

An illustrative example of multitarget toxicity has been observed in TMLs containing α,β -unsaturated ketone moiety within the lactone ring. Stagonolide A, previously identified as a potent fungal phytotoxin¹³, has also demonstrated antimicrobial, antialgal, cytotoxic, insecticidal, and plant growth inhibitory activities. Similar broad-spectrum effects have been reported for its acetylated derivative as well as for the C-7 oxidized stagonolide K⁹, pyrenolide C¹⁰ and humicolactone¹⁴ (figure 2).

Figure 2. Chemical structure of TMLs exhibiting non-target toxicity

Comparison of these ketones with their hydroxyl counterparts clearly suggests that the observed biological effects are associated with the presence of the α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group, regardless of its position in the lactone ring. Notably, conjugation of a carbon-carbon double bond with a carboxyl group does not appear to induce similar toxicity, underscoring the unique contribution of the conjugated ketone to the multitarget activity of TMLs¹⁰. Additionally some authors associate cytotoxicity of presaccharothriolide X¹⁵, colletoin A and colletofragarone A2¹⁶ with the presence of α,β -unsaturated ketone in their structures (figure 3).

Figure 3. Selected cytotoxic TMLs with α,β -unsaturated keto group

Epoxy ring

The influence of the epoxide ring in TMLs molecules on their biological activity is ambiguous and strongly dependent on its location in the lactone ring. A decent example would be bellidisin D, produced by *Phoma bellidis*. This compound demonstrates potent cytotoxicity against multiple human cancer cell lines (IC₅₀ 3.40-15.25 μ M) while its regioisomer 5,6-epoxypinolidoxin is inactive as well as pinolidoxin itself¹⁷ (figure 4). Recently discovered 5,6-epoxidized TML xylatolide B showing no significant cytotoxic and antimicrobial activity supports these observations¹⁸.

Figure 4. The effect of epoxide scaffold on toxicity profile of TMLs

Substantial changes in toxicity profile caused by epoxide moiety was demonstrated within the stagonolide E/curvulide A couple (figure 4). While stagonolide E exhibits strong aphicidal activity and weak phytotoxicity, curvulide A shows a reverse profile, acting as a potent phytotoxin with a slight aphicidal effect. The C-4,C-5 position of an epoxy ring seems to be an important feature as the C-7,C-8 epoxides presented in that research were inactive in the aforementioned bioassays¹⁰.

Absolute configuration of C-7 and C-2 chiral carbons

Only a few studies have examined the effect of chiral center stereoconfiguration on the biological activity of TMLs. Lu et al.¹¹⁻¹² analyzed the cytotoxicity of cytospolides A–P and found that, with few exceptions, the 2S epimers exhibited stronger activity against the A-549 cancer cell line (IC₅₀ 2.05–5.15 µg/mL) compared to their 2R counterparts. Dalinova et al.⁹ reported a striking difference in seed germination effect between the semisynthetic acetates of herbarumin I and its C-7 epimer, stagonolide J (figure 5).

Figure 5. Effect of chiral center stereoconfiguration on the phyto- and cytotoxicity of selected TMLs.

Notably, both studies indicate that the presence of a C-8 acetyl group significantly alters the toxicity profile of the parent lactones. However, due to the lack of systematic comparisons, the broader impact of acylation on TML bioactivity is unclear and remains to be fully understood.

Olefinic and allyl alcohol motifs in the C-2–C-7 region

Because most TMLs contain one or more olefinic bonds, it is challenging to evaluate their individual contribution to toxicity apart from the influence of adjacent functional groups. However, in specific cases the role of the carbon-carbon double bond becomes markedly apparent. The comparison between stagonolide D and curvulides B₁/B₂ serves as a clear example. While stagonolide D is inactive in a variety of bioassays, the curvulides B₁/B₂, which feature a C-2–C-3 olefin fragment, exhibit both phyto- and entomotoxicity. This double bond also influences the chemical behavior of the molecule, rendering curvulides B a dynamic mixture of interconverting epimers, in contrast to the stereochemically stable stagonolide D¹⁰ (figure 6).

Figure 6. Chemical structures of stagonolide D and curvulides B₁/B₂

Consistent efforts to identify structural features responsible for the phytotoxicity of TMLs have been undertaken by Evidente et al. Their resulting hypothesis suggests that oxidative modifications in the C-2 to C-4 region lead to a decrease or complete loss of phytotoxic activity⁸. Most known phytotoxic TMLs support this trend, with few exceptions – such as pinolidoxin and curvulide A – that retain activity despite functionalization in this region. These outliers suggest that the original hypothesis may benefit from refinement: specifically, that *the presence of hydrogen bond donor groups, such as hydroxyls, within the C-2–C-4 region is associated with reduced phytotoxicity*. Noteworthy that plant growth inhibition activity prediction is substantially less reliable by this criteria and obviously requires more data to be acquired.

Despite the structural diversity of TMLs, a recurring motif is evident among representatives with confirmed phytotoxic activity³. In particular, analysis of relatively simple examples – such as putaminoxin A, stagonolides K and F, hypocreolide A, and herbarumin III (figure 7) – reveals a consistent presence of an allyl alcohol moiety in the C-5 to C-7 region. In contrast, the length of the alkyl substituent at C-9 appears to have little or no influence on phytotoxicity.

Figure 7. Typical structures of phytotoxic TMLs

Conclusion and perspectives

Ten-membered lactones (TMLs) represent a structurally diverse class of secondary metabolites. Despite their frequent occurrence in fungal metabolomes and their broad biological activity, they remain insufficiently characterized in terms of structure-activity relationship (SAR). Overcoming this knowledge gap will make them promising candidates for the development of new lead compounds in both pharmaceutical and agrochemical applications. This short review highlights several preliminary SAR trends: the α,β -unsaturated ketone correlates with broad toxicity; allyl alcohol motifs in the C-5–C-7 region are common in phytotoxic TMLs; and hydroxylation in the C-2–C-4 region often reduces phytotoxicity. Stereochemistry at C-2 and C-7 influences both phyto- and cytotoxicity. By contrast, epoxides and olefins show context-dependent effects. However, traditional SAR approaches, based on linear structural comparisons, are of limited applicability to complex, polycyclic TML derivatives. Constructing more reliable SAR models will require substantial expansion of the dataset – through the discovery of new natural representatives, the preparation of synthetic analogs. Additionally, robust multitarget bioactivity profiling and the integration of cheminformatics tools, such as molecular fingerprints and neural networks, might play an essential role in capturing subtle activity-driving features and improve predictive capacity.

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References

1. Atanasov et al. *Nat Rev Drug Discov* 2021, 20 (3), 200–216. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41573-020-00114-z>
2. Sparks et al. *Pest Management Science* 2021, 78 (2), 399–408. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.6653>
3. Dubovik et al. *Nat. Prod. Rep.* 2024, 41 (1), 85–112. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3np00013c>
4. Berestetskiy, A. RU Patent 2,701,817 C1, Oct 1, 2019.
5. Schmidt, B. *Prog. Chem. Org. Nat. Prod.* 2021, 1–57. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64853-4_1
6. Ehrlich et al. *J. Org. Chem.* 2019, 84 (6), 3132–3147. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.joc.8b02999>
7. Sippl et al. *Molecules* 2021, 26 (2), 250. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26020250>
8. Evidente et al. *J. Nat. Prod.* 2008, 71, 31–34. <https://doi.org/10.1021/np0703038>
9. Dalinova et al. *J. Fungi* 2021, 7, 829. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof7100829>
10. Fedorov et al. *J. Nat. Prod.* 2024 87 (4), 914–923. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jnatprod.3c01216>
11. Lu et al. *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* 2011, 28, 5452–5459. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejoc.201100675>
12. Lu et al. *J Org Chem* 2011, 76, 9699–9710. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jo201755v>
13. Yuzikhin et al. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 2007, 55 (19), 7707–7711. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf070742c>
14. Fischer et al. *Natural Product Letters*, 1995, 7, 303–308. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10575639508043226>
15. Lu et al. *Org. Lett.* 2018, 20 (15), 4406–4410. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.orglett.8b01535>
16. Sadahiro et al. *J. Nat. Prod.* 2021, 84 (12), 3131–3137. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jnatprod.1c00913>
17. Wang et al. *Phytochemistry Letters* 2019, 29, 41–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytol.2018.11.012>
18. Koliye et al. *Z. Naturforsch. C.* 2024, 79 (11–12), 371–376. <https://doi.org/10.1515/znc-2023-0091>
19. Tyutereva et al. *Toxins* 2023, 15, 234. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins15040234>